

The Cyclic Processes involved in the Manufacture of Sodium Nitrate from Chilean Caliche.

By MOHAMMED ABDUL HAMID.

Sodium nitrate occurs in large quantities in South America and is generally known as Chile Saltpetre. The crude material from which the Chile saltpetre is manufactured is commonly called *caliche*.

The main constituents of the water soluble products of most of the nitrate deposits of Chile are the nitrates, sulphates and chlorides of sodium and in smaller quantities those of calcium, magnesium and potassium. To these may be added the chlorates, borates and iodates and salts of aluminium, iron and chromium, which occur in very small quantities.

The raw material is usually crushed to small pieces and then leached with water according to various modifications of the Shank's process. The *Aqua Vieja* or the cold extract is then taken to the boiling tanks where the necessary amount of evaporation is carried out. The *caldo* or the hot liquor then goes to the crystallising vats where it is allowed to cool and the crystallised salts removed by filtration. The mother-liquor, after the addition of the requisite amount of water to it is used again for the leaching operations.

As mentioned above the main constituents of the water-soluble products of most of the caliches are the sulphates, nitrates and chlorides of sodium. The solubility of sodium chloride in nitrate liquors is not much affected by change in temperature and since it occurs as a solid saturant at all stages, its presence may be disregarded. The system, $H_2O-Na_2SO_4-NaNO_3$, at 25° has been recently investigated by the author (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129 203). The addition of sodium chloride to this system will cause a slight change in the solubilities of the two salts but will not affect the nature of this system since sodium chloride is not known to form any compounds with either sodium sulphate or sodium nitrate. We shall therefore suppose that the relations in this system at 25° are those shown in Fig. I even in the presence of excess of sodium chloride. This figure is taken from the paper above mentioned,

It will be seen by reference to Fig. I, that the system $H_2O-Na_2SO_4-NaNO_3$ at 25° is complicated by the existence of a hydrated double salt which is composed of one molecule of sodium sulphate, one molecule of sodium nitrate and one molecule of water. The composition of this compound is represented by the point D in weight percentages in Fig. I. The following points may carefully be noted in this figure:—

(i) Points in the area cAD represent complexes of the solution c and of the two solids sodium sulphate and the compound D in varying proportions.

(ii) Points in the area dDB represent complexes of the solution d with mixtures of sodium nitrate and the compound D of varying proportions.

(iii) Points in the area DAB represent dry mixtures of sodium nitrate, sodium sulphate and the compound D . No solution can exist here because there is not enough water to combine with sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate to form the compound D .

In order that the phenomena which occur during the leaching of caliche may be properly understood, we shall study the behaviour of dry mixtures of sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate of varying compositions on the gradual and isothermal addition of water at 25° . Suppose n_1 and n_2 represent the number of mols. of sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate in a given nitrate-sulphate mixture. Three cases may be distinguished. When,

$$(i) \quad \frac{n_1}{n_2} = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad n_1 = n_2$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{n_1}{n_2} < 1 \quad \text{or} \quad n_2 > n_1$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{n_1}{n_2} > 1 \quad \text{or} \quad n_1 > n_2$$

or expressed in proportions by weight, when,

$$(i) \quad \frac{w_1}{w_2} = \frac{85}{142} \quad \text{or} \quad w_1 = \cdot 6w_2$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{w_1}{w_2} < \frac{85}{142} \quad \text{or} \quad w_1 < \cdot 6w_2$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{w_1}{w_2} > \frac{85}{142} \quad \text{or} \quad w_1 > \cdot 6w_2$$

Case I. When $n_1 = n_2$ *i.e.*, when the mixture contains equal number of mols. of sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate. It is clear that when a certain amount (n mols.) of water is added to such a mixture, the whole of sodium nitrate will combine with the whole of sodium sulphate to form the hydrated sulphate-nitrate compound D . We shall see the various changes which take place on the gradual and isothermal addition of water to such a mixture at 25° . Expressed in weight percentages,

$$w_1 + w_2 = 100$$

$$w_1 = .6w$$

$\therefore w_1 = 37.5$ and $w_2 = 62.5$ *i.e.*, the mixture contains 37.5 parts by weight of sodium nitrate and 62.5 parts by weight of sodium sulphate. The composition of this mixture is represented by the point C in Fig. I. On the gradual and isothermal addition of water to this mixture at 25° , the composition of the complex so formed would change along the line CW in the direction CW . It may be seen that the point D' which represents the composition of the nitrate-sulphate compound lies on the line CW , *i.e.*, it contains sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate in the same proportions as is contained by the dry mixture C . Suppose so much of the water is added to the mixture C that the composition of the complex is represented by a point on the line CW between the points C and D . Since this point lies in the area DAB , it is impossible for any solution to exist (see above) and the complex will therefore consist only of dry mixtures of sodium sulphate, sodium nitrate and the compound D . When so much of the water has been added to the mixture C that the composition of the complex is represented by the point D , the whole of sodium nitrate combines with the whole of sodium sulphate and the whole of water added to form a homogeneous solid phase of the composition D , *i.e.*, the nitrate-sulphate compound. From this point onward therefore we may regard further dilution as the dissolution of the compound D in water. This dissolution is ~~not~~ normal, since water causes the dissociation of a portion of the solid D into its respective components and the solid in contact with solution is of a heterogeneous character consisting of a mixture of the compound D and one of its dissociation products, sodium sulphate. Suppose the composition of the complex at any one time is represented by the point C_1 . This point represents a complex of the solution c and of a mixture of solid D and solid sodium sulphate

in the proportion of,

$$\frac{C_1 C'_1}{c C'_1} \text{ parts of the solution } c \text{ and } \frac{c C'_1}{c C'_1} \text{ parts of } D + \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4.$$

The proportion of D and Na_2SO_4 in the solid mixture is given by the ratio in which the line cC_1 , when produced divides the line DA , *i.e.*,

$$\frac{AC'_1}{AD} \text{ parts of } D \text{ and } \frac{C'_1 D}{AD} \text{ parts of } \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4.$$

In order to keep the composition of the solution c constant, more of the compound D dissociates on increasing additions of water. Thus when the composition of the complex is represented by the point C_1 , the proportions of the compound D and of sodium sulphate in the solid mixture are,

$$\frac{C'_1 D}{AD} \text{ parts of } \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ and } \frac{AC'_1}{AD} \text{ parts of } D.$$

It may be observed here that the whole of the sodium nitrate which is produced by the dissociation of the compound D is dissolved while the solution dissolves only a portion of the sodium sulphate which is thus produced, the rest being precipitated as such in the solid form. Therefore on the addition of increasing amounts of water, the proportion of sodium sulphate in the solid phase goes on increasing while that of the compound D goes on decreasing and the solution in all these changes retains the constant composition c . When so much of the water has been added that it effects the complete dissociation of the compound D , this compound disappears as a solid phase. On further additions of water therefore, the composition of the solution changes along the curve cb in the direction cb *i.e.*, in a direction in which the solution contains diminishing quantities of sodium nitrate. We are not concerned here with these changes. Our only object has been to show that on the isothermal addition of water at 25° to a dry sulphate-nitrate mixture which contains equal number of molecules of sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate, the strongest solution that can be obtained with respect to sodium nitrate concentration is of the composition c .

Case II. When $n_2 > n_1$, *i.e.*, when the number of molecules of sodium sulphate exceeds the number of molecules of sodium nitrate

in the dry mixture or expressed in proportions by weight when the weight of sodium nitrate is less than three-fifth of the weight of sodium sulphate in the dry mixture. The composition of one such mixture is given by the point E in Fig. I in weight percentages. When so much of the water is added to the mixture E that the composition of the dry mixture is represented by the point E_1 , the whole of the sodium nitrate present combines with the whole of water added and three-fifth parts by weight of the whole of sodium sulphate present to form the compound D and the excess of sodium sulphate remains as such in the solid form. E_1 is therefore a dry mixture of

$$\frac{AE_1}{AD} \text{ parts of } D \text{ and } \frac{E_1D}{AD} \text{ parts of } Na_2SO_4.$$

The various changes that occur on the gradual addition of water at 25° to this mixture along the line EW in the direction EW can be deduced in the same manner as in the first case by reference to Fig. I. It will be seen here that as in the former case the composition of the strongest solution with respect to sodium nitrate concentration which can be obtained from a dry mixture in which the molar ratio of sodium nitrate to sodium sulphate is less than one is given by the point c in Fig. I.

Case III. When $n_1 > n_2$, *i.e.*, when the number of molecules of sodium nitrate exceeds the number of molecules of sodium sulphate in the dry mixture. Suppose

$$n_1 = n_2 + x.$$

When n_2 mols. of water are added to this mixture they will combine with n_2 mols. of sodium nitrate and the whole of sodium sulphate to form n_2 mols. of the compound D and the solid mixture will at this stage contain n_2 mols. of D and x mols. of free solid sodium nitrate. These relations may be expressed in weight percentages as follows:—

$$w_1 + w_2 = 100$$

Suppose $w_1 = .6w_2 + x,$

and $w_2 = 40$

then $x_1 = w_1 - .6w_2 = 36$

i.e., in a mixture which contains 40 parts by weight of sodium sulphate and 60 parts by weight of sodium nitrate, only 36 parts by weight of sodium nitrate will be free to dissolve as such and the remaining 24 parts by weight of sodium nitrate will combine with 40 parts by weight of sodium sulphate to form the compound *D* when water interaction takes place. The same thing can be shown by reference to Fig. I. The composition of a mixture which contains 40 parts by weight of sodium sulphate and 60 parts by weight of sodium nitrate is given by the point *F* in Fig. I. The composition of the mixture *F* can be represented either by reference to the line *AB* or to the line *CB*. Referring it to the line *CB* we have the composition of *F* in weight percentages,

$$F = \frac{100CF}{CB} \text{ parts of } B \text{ and } \frac{100FB}{CB} \text{ parts of } C.$$

We have seen in Case I that when $AB=100$, $CB=62.5$, so that

$$CF=CB-FB=62.5-40 = 22.5.$$

$$\therefore F = \frac{100 \times 22.5}{62.5} \text{ parts of } B \text{ and } \frac{100 \times 40}{62.5} \text{ parts of } C.$$

i.e., 36 parts by weight of *B* or sodium nitrate and 64 parts by weight of *C*.

We started with a mixture of 60 parts by weight of sodium nitrate and 40 parts by weight of sodium sulphate. Out of 60 parts, sodium nitrate is distributed as 36 parts in the phase *B* or is present as such and (60-36) or 24 parts in the mixture *C* which also contains all the 40 parts of sodium sulphate present in the original mixture. It may be pointed out that this is only an imaginary distribution. The actual distribution of sodium nitrate only takes place in the presence of water.

On the addition of water at 25° to the mixture *F*, the composition of the mixture changes along the line *FW* in the direction *FW*. Between the points *F* and *F*₁, it is not possible for any solution to exist and points on the line *F*₁*F* between the points *F* and *F*₁ represent compositions of dry mixtures of *C*, the compound *D* and the phase *B* or free sodium nitrate, in other words on account of insufficient quantity of water, only a part of the mixture *C* is converted into the compound *D*. When so much water has been added that

the composition of the mixture is represented by the point F_1 , the whole of the mixture C is converted into the compound D and the point F_1 represents a mixture of the compound D and the phase B or free sodium nitrate in the proportion of

$$\frac{DF_1}{DB} \text{ parts of } B \text{ or free sodium nitrate and } \frac{F_1B}{DB} \text{ parts of the com-}$$

pound D . On the addition of increasing quantities of water, the mixture F yields complexes of the solution d with mixtures of solid sodium nitrate and the compound D in varying proportions. When the composition of the complex is represented by the point F_2 , it contains

$$\frac{F_2F'_2}{F'_2d} \text{ parts of the solution } d \text{ and } \frac{F_2d}{F'_2d} \text{ parts of the mixture } F'_2,$$

which contains

$$\frac{DF'_2}{DB} \text{ parts of solid sodium nitrate and } \frac{F'_2B}{DB} \text{ parts of the}$$

compound D . On further additions of water when the composition of the complex is represented by the point F_3 , the solution d is in contact with a mixture which contains,

$$\frac{DF'_3}{DB} \text{ parts of solid sodium nitrate and } \frac{F'_3B}{DB} \text{ parts of the solid}$$

compound D . It is clear therefore that on increasing additions of water the proportion of free sodium nitrate decreases and that of the compound D increases in the solid mixture while the solution retains the constant composition d . When so much of the water has been added that the composition of the complex is represented by the point F_4 , sodium nitrate disappears as a solid phase and the solution d is in contact with the solid compound D only. If at this stage the solution d is separated from the solid compound D by filtration, we have,

$$\frac{DF_4}{Dd} \text{ parts of the solution } d, \text{ and } \frac{F_4d}{Dd} \text{ parts of the compound } D.$$

If this solid compound D is dissolved separately in water, we have shown in Case I that the composition of the strongest solution with respect to sodium nitrate concentration which can be obtained from it is that represented by the point c . To sum up we can say that on the isothermal addition of water to a dry mixture of sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate in which the number of molecules of

sodium nitrate exceeds the number of molecules of sodium sulphate by x , we can get an amount of the solution d corresponding to x only *i.e.*, to the free nitrate only and an additional solution of the remaining (combined) nitrate at a maximum concentration of sodium nitrate equal to that contained by the solution c .

Very recently a process has been invented by Guggenheim brothers in America, who claim that 'their invention will make possible a leaching process operating in such a manner as to permit a cold or tepid leaching of caliche in a cyclical and orderly manner, which will accomplish substantial dissolution of all the sodium nitrate in normal caliches and will permit the production of the entire solution as strong solution approaching or exceeding the solubility of free nitrate at 25°, in contradistinction to the production of a portion of the solution at a maximum concentration of the nitrate equal to that contained by the solution c , the production of which is maintained by the authorities in the industry to-day as necessary to obtain commercially satisfactory extraction.' They state that an efficient and desirable way of preventing the disturbing influence of the nitrate-sulphate compound is by controlling and properly proportioning the content in the caliches and in the leaching solutions of the salts of magnesium, calcium and potassium, which have in the past practice of the industry been considered unimportant constituents, and to the presence of which no significance in this connection was attached. These salts can be characterised as those which are able to exert preferential combining affinities for the sulphate radicle group (SO_4) or for sodium sulphate. The chief of these are salts of calcium, potassium and magnesium. Stripped of the garb of technicalities, the Guggenheim process can be easily explained by the following example:—

Although the quaternary system, $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4-\text{NaNO}_3-\text{MgSO}_4-\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, at 25° has not been worked out or at least the results have never been published, it is probable that the relations in this system will not be very different from those shown in Fig. II. Jackman and Brown (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 691) have shown that the only solid phases in the system, $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{MgSO}_4-\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, at 25° are $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, but it is very likely that the hexa-hydrate of magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and even Kieserite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) may appear as solid phases at 25° in the above quaternary system. Since it is immaterial for the present purpose whether the lower hydrates of magnesium sulphate appear

in the quaternary system or not, they are not shown in Fig. II. From this figure it will be seen that all along the curve xy between the points x and y , the quaternary solutions are in equilibrium with two solids, sodium nitrate in the free state and a hydrated double salt of sodium sulphate and magnesium sulphate of the composition, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, commonly known as Astrakanite. The point x represents the composition of a quaternary invariant solution in equilibrium with three solids, sodium nitrate, Astrakanite and the sulphate-nitrate compound D . The addition of a small quantity of magnesium nitrate (or of magnesium sulphate) to the quaternary invariant solution x , in contact with the three solids with which it is in equilibrium will split up a portion of the solid compound D (nitrate-sulphate compound) into its respective components and the sodium sulphate thus produced will combine with the magnesium salts added to form Astrakanite setting free solid sodium nitrate. The mechanism of the phase reactions in equilibrium at the quaternary invariant point x will probably be as follows:

where a , b , c , d , and e are any positive quantities of the substances that take part in the reaction and D and D_1 represent the sulphate-nitrate compound and Astrakanite respectively.

On the increasing additions of magnesium nitrate to the complex of the invariant solution x the above reaction will occur. This reaction will leave the actual composition of the solution x unaltered. When so much of the magnesium nitrate is added that it effects the complete conversion of the solid compound D into free sodium nitrate and Astrakanite, the compound D disappears as a solid phase and the composition of the solution alters along the curve xy .

From the above discussion it is clear that by maintaining a sufficient amount of the magnesium salts in the leaching solutions as well as in the raw material, the whole of the sulphate-nitrate compound can be decomposed, the sodium sulphate thus produced combining with magnesium sulphate to form Astrakanite leaving behind free sodium nitrate. If the amount of sodium sulphate exceeds the amount of magnesium sulphate (mol. for mol.), the excess of sodium sulphate will combine with sodium nitrate to form the sulphate-nitrate compound so that even if the quantity of magnesium salts added is insufficient to decompose the whole of the sulphate-nitrate

compound, it will greatly reduce the proportion of the sodium sulphate available to combine with sodium nitrate.

If heat is now abstracted from the solution by artificial refrigeration, it will cause the precipitation of pure or practically pure sodium nitrate if the temperature to which it is cooled is not so low as to effect the separation of magnesium nitrate present in the leaching solution.

It may be pointed out here that the solubility of sodium sulphate in nitrate liquors decreases with the rise of temperature and consequently this salt will not separate out on cooling up to a certain temperature, below which the hydrated sodium sulphate or Glauber's salt will come out. The point of transition may however be further lowered in the presence of certain salts, *e.g.*, borates, iodates etc., which may be present in the raw material or which may be added to the leaching solution or to the solution after leaching and before refrigeration. The lowest temperature should not however be below that which would cause the precipitation of these salts. These salts, the object of which is simply to lower the transition temperature of sodium sulphate and Glauber's salt, are termed minor salts.

What has been said about Astrakanite is also true of other double sulphates, *i.e.*, calcium potassium sulphate or Syngenite and calcium sodium sulphate or Glauberite. These are called 'protective compounds' since they protect the sodium nitrate from combining with sodium sulphate. The salts such as magnesium nitrate in the above example are termed 'stabilising agents', because in the presence of these salts the double sulphates are stabilised and remain insoluble.

The author is indebted to Professor F. G. Donnan for his very kind help and interest in this work.